

Anomaly detection in Launch vehicle systems during simulations using machine learning

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Abstract

Launch vehicles play a critical role in modern space exploration, where precision and reliability are paramount. Reliable and safe operation of launch vehicle systems is critical for the success of space missions. Identifying deviations from expected behaviour is essential for preventing potential catastrophic failures during launch missions. Anomalies that may compromise system performance can be challenging to identify, especially during simulations where various complex interactions are at play. The project addresses this challenge by utilising machine learning algorithms to analyse data generated during the simulation of launch vehicle systems under various conditions. This data includes a wide range of information, providing a comprehensive view of system behaviour. Through machine learning, we aim to identify potential anomalies or system irregularities. By harnessing the power of these algorithms, we can detect subtle patterns and outliers that may be difficult to capture. The project enhances fault detection process during stimulation by leveraging the capabilities of machine learning, this project contributes to the advancement of anomaly detection methodologies in aerospace engineering. In conclusion, this project represents a significant step toward enhancing anomaly detection using computer software.

Keywords: Anomaly Detection, DBScan, Vehicle Rate : Pitch, Yaw, Roll, Silhouette Score, epsilon

I. INTRODUCTION

Anomaly detection in launch vehicles is an intricate process vital for the success and safety of space missions. The launch vehicle's sophisticated sensor suite continuously monitors a plethora of critical parameters, such as temperature, pressure, acceleration, vibration, and fuel levels, throughout every phase of the mission. Real-time data from these sensors undergoes meticulous analysis employing advanced algorithms, including statistical methods, machine learning models, and signal processing techniques, to swiftly detect any deviations from expected behaviour that could signal potential faults or malfunctions.

In addition to traditional anomaly detection methods, some advanced anomaly detection algorithms, such as DBSCAN (Density-Based Spatial Clustering of Applications with Noise), are being explored for launch vehicle monitoring. DBSCAN is particularly adept at identifying spatial clusters of data points, making it suitable for detecting anomalies within complex, multi-dimensional datasets like those generated by launch vehicle sensors. By clustering the data based on density, DBSCAN can effectively identify outliers that do not belong to any cluster, flagging them as potential anomalies.

Furthermore, the concept of vehicle rate, which refers to the rate of change of various parameters over time, is often incorporated into anomaly detection strategies. By monitoring the rate of change of critical parameters such as Pitch rate, Yaw rate and Roll rate, can be detected not only based on absolute values but also on abnormal trends or abrupt changes in these rates. This approach adds another layer of sophistication to anomaly detection systems, enabling them to detect subtle deviations in vehicle behaviour that may not be apparent when considering absolute parameter values alone.

Overall, the combination of traditional anomaly detection techniques, advanced algorithms like DBSCAN, and the incorporation of vehicle rate monitoring ensures that launch vehicles are comprehensively monitored, allowing for the swift detection and mitigation of anomalies, thereby enhancing mission safety and success.

II. RELATED WORKS

[1] Hundman et al. (2018) propose an approach for spacecraft anomaly detection using LSTM recurrent neural networks (RNNs) and nonparametric dynamic thresholding. They address challenges in spacecraft telemetry, suggesting LSTM RNNs for prediction performance and interpretability. Additionally, they introduce a nonparametric dynamic thresholding approach to evaluate residuals. Experimental results using real-world data from missions like Mars Science Laboratory (MSL) rover Curiosity and Soil Moisture Active Passive (SMAP) satellite validate their approach. The authors offer open-source methodologies and data for broader research community use. [2] Another paper by Salima Omar, Asri Ngadi, Hamid H. Jebur provided an overview of research directions in anomaly detection, discussing various supervised algorithms such as Neural Networks, Support Vector Machines, and Decision Trees, and unsupervised methods like K-Means, Self-organizing maps, and One-Class SVM. The effectiveness of supervised methods was noted in scenarios where test data contain no unknown attacks, while unsupervised methods performed well in other situations. [3] Additionally, Seungdong Yoa, Seungjun Lee; Chiyeon Kim, and Hyunwoo J Kim proposed a framework for unsupervised anomaly detection utilizing self-supervised learning, achieving an average success percentage. [4] Furthermore, an efficient online anomaly detection model based on Broad Learning System (BLS) was established by Chong Wang et al. for identifying anomalies in high-speed train braking systems, emphasizing BLS's efficiency and adaptability. [5] Lastly, a method for automated early detection of anomalies in streaming network operation data was proposed by Mehdi Shajari; Hongxiang Geng; Kaixuan Hu; Alberto Leon-Garcia, although limitations were noted regarding the system's insensitivity to anomalies with smaller fluctuations during normal operation. [6] Gao, Yang, and Xu propose an unsupervised anomaly detection approach for spacecraft based on normal behavior clustering (1). This method aims to automatically detect anomalies within unlabelled historical telemetry data. The approach involves removing abnormal data, constructing a system's normal behavior model through normal data clustering, and monitoring spacecraft status at runtime to identify deviations from the established model. The authors highlight the importance of early anomaly detection in complex spacecraft systems due to the challenges of repairing or replacing damaged components in space. While traditional limit checking techniques lack flexibility, intelligent monitoring systems like rule-based expert systems or model-based reasoning methods face challenges in acquiring accurate system behavior models. In contrast, data-driven approaches leverage machine learning and data mining technologies to extract information directly from vast telemetry data. The proposed method eliminates the need for complete and accurate expert knowledge or models by clustering normal behavior from telemetry data. The paper concludes with discussions on experimental results and potential areas for future research.

III. PROPOSED METHOD

Figure 1 depicts the proposed method for anomaly detection using DBSCAN

Fig. 1: Proposed method

Load Data: Load the dataset containing the features you want to analyze for anomalies.

Preprocess Data: Perform any necessary data preprocessing steps, such as scaling or normalization, to prepare the data for clustering.

Choose Parameters: Select the epsilon (ϵ) and minimum samples (minPts) parameters for DBSCAN. Epsilon defines the maximum distance between two samples for them to be considered as in the same neighbourhood, while minPts specifies the minimum number of samples in a neighbourhood for a point to be considered as a core point.

Fit DBSCAN: Apply the DBSCAN algorithm to the preprocessed data, using the chosen epsilon and minPts values.

Anomaly Detection: Identify anomalies by finding points that are not assigned to any cluster.

Label Clusters: Assign cluster labels to the data points based on the clustering results. Points that are not assigned to any cluster are considered as anomalies.

Output Results: Output the anomalies found by the DBSCAN algorithm, along with any relevant information for further analysis or action

Algorithm :

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Algorithm 1: DBSCAN Algorithm
Input  : points, minSamples
Output: cluster, type
for point in points do
    if neighbors[point].count() ≥ minSamples then
        corePoints.push(point)
        type[point] = 'core point'
    end
end
for cp in corePoints do
    if cluster[cp] is NULL then
        ++clusterCount
        cluster[cp] = clusterCount
        queue = []
        while not queue.empty() do
            for neigh in neighbors[cp] do
                cluster[neigh] = clusterCount
                if type[neigh] == 'core point' then
                    queue.push(neigh)
                end
            else
                type[neigh] = 'non-core point'
            end
        end
    end
end
for point in points do
    if type[point] is NULL then
        type[point] = 'outlier'
    end
end

```

Fig. 2: DBScan Algorithm

There are 2 major hyperparameters to choose when applying DBSCAN:

- epsilon – the maximum distance between 2 points for them to be considered neighbors of one another (e.g.: 0.01, 0.5, 2 etc.)
- min_samples – the minimum number of neighbors a point needs to have to be considered a core point (e.g.: 3, 5, 10 etc.). This includes the starting point

Having selected them, we can start applying the algorithm:

First, we determine which points are core points based on how many neighbours they have. If this number is greater than min_samples, we found a core point. The next step is going through the list of core points and spreading the current cluster to other close points. For each new point, if it is a core point, we will use it to propagate the cluster. If not, we mark it as a non-core point. Finally, all points that have not been assigned to a cluster are marked as outliers.

IV. RESULT

Silhouette Score: 0.57

Silhouette Score: 0.54

The provided content consists of two graphs displaying vehicle rates (pitch, yaw, and roll) plotted against time. The x-axis represents time, with increments of 20 milliseconds, while the y-axis depicts the vehicle rates. Each graph corresponds to a different test dataset.

In both graphs, anomalous points are highlighted in red, indicating deviations from expected vehicle behavior. These anomalies could signify irregularities or unexpected occurrences in the vehicle's movements. Additionally, it's mentioned that the silhouette score for the first dataset is 0.57, while for the second dataset it is 0.54. The silhouette score is a measure of how similar an object is to its own cluster compared to other clusters. In this context, it suggests the degree of cohesion within the dataset clusters, with higher scores indicating better-defined clusters.

V. CONCLUSION

In summation, the detailed examination of the Data Flow Diagram (DFD) illuminates a sophisticated and cohesive architecture designed for the effective implementation of anomaly detection in launch vehicles. The external entities, the Launch Vehicle Telemetry System, and the Machine Learning Model, emerge as pivotal contributors to the system's functionality, each playing a distinct yet interconnected role. The array of processes, encompassing Data Acquisition and Preprocessing, Feature Selection, Machine Learning Model Training, Real-time Monitoring, and Model Update, delineates a comprehensive workflow, underscoring the multi-faceted approach adopted for anomaly detection. The integration of advanced machine learning methodologies, particularly evident in the utilization of a Historical Data Store for training, signifies a forward-looking strategy aimed at leveraging past mission data for improved anomaly prediction. The intricate data flows depicted in the diagram not only elucidate the directional movement of information but also highlight the dynamic and reciprocal relationships between different stages of the anomaly detection process. The concept of the Feedback Loop introduces a crucial element of adaptability and continuous learning, acknowledging the evolving nature of launch missions and the necessity for the system to refine its anomaly detection capabilities iteratively. In essence, the DFD serves as a comprehensive blueprint, showcasing the interplay of components and processes crucial for anomaly detection. This not only reinforces the reliability and safety of launch vehicle missions but also lays the groundwork for future enhancements and refinements, emphasizing the project's commitment to continuous improvement in the realm of space exploration.

VI. REFERENCES

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